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Executive Summary

The purpose of this work is to test the installation processes and the workflows of the packages described in this document. WP9 has successfully installed following packages: Clark, kraken2, kaiju, SPAdes, QUASt and Metaphlan2. This deliverable is the first step towards the implementation of metagenomics tools into Hopsworks; the HEAP PaaS.

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1 Project description

This deliverable test the installation processes and the workflows of the packages Clark, kraken2, kaiju, SPAdes, QUASt and Metaphlan2, which are bioinformatics tools useful for metagenomics analysis.

2 Project Directory

The project main directory is placed in:

```
/lu/topola/temp/ss426665/Praktyki
```

The reason for the project directory placement is that the packages can produce large amounts of data. Inside the Praktyki directory there are following directories:

- A. **metagenomics_data** → holds the test data in four directories:
 - a. *paired* → Paired matched trimmed, quality filtered data in R1 and R2 files per sample. Used for the pipeline tests.
 - b. *total* → One file for each sample contained with trimmed, quality filtered, paired matched and unpaired reads.
 - c. *nh* → One file for each sample with trimmed, quality filtered, excluded human reads (unmapped reads to human genome were the ones left). Probably the best dataset since human reads are missing, but I was unable to use it inside the pipeline tests, because of a single PE file while pipelines use single SE files or R1 and R2 PE files.
 - d. *raw* → Raw untrimmed read in R1 and R2 files for each sample.
- B. **PrivateModules** → holds the directories where the module files for the packages installed in the project are placed.
- C. **Programy** → holds the packages installation directories, where the packages were installed.
- D. **tests** → holds the output directories of the pipeline tests with the exemplary shell scripts for the pipeline workflow (db directories hold databases, db_scripts hold database creation scripts, classify_scripts hold scripts used during the classification step, classify_output hold test outputs form packages).
- E. **tmp** → holds temporary files downloaded during the package installation step.

3 Packages

1.1. Clark v.1.2.6.1

1.1.1. Package overview

CLARK package is a tool written in C++. It is used for rapid classification of any DNA/RNA sequences. Tool can use multiple input data formats such as raw reads, constructed contigs and scaffold assemblies to classify against the reference sequences in the same variation of formats. Input sequences are called "objects", while references are called "targets".

CLARK package includes three classifiers:

- A. **CLARK** – the default classifier, that requires significant amounts of RAM.
- B. **CLARK-I** – classifier used when the amount of RAM is limited (works with lighter reference database)
- C. **CLARK-S** – classifier used with more RAM than default version, performing "spaced" k-mers classification with higher sensitivity. One used in the pipeline tests.

Package also contains a few scripts facilitating the usage of the classifiers in which couple should be highlighted:

- A. ***set_targets.sh*** allows to create a valid database of genomic sequences with given arguments like fungi, bacteria, viruses, plasmid, plastid, protozoa, and custom. The script also allows for the choice of genetic level, which should be used during the classification. Genetic levels include species (default), genus, family, order, class, and phylum.
- B. ***buildSpacedDB.sh*** allows for the build of the discriminative spaced k-mers from given database. It needs to be executed before the CLARK-S run.
- C. ***classify_metagenome.sh*** which is responsible for invoking the CLARK classifiers.

1.1.2. Package installation on Okeanos

Clark-S needs GCC v4.4 or higher to be compiled. For the installation setup the package was downloaded and uncompressed via wget. Then we switched the Programming Environment to default GNU. The next step was installing the script and moving the package files to the Program directory. Commands used:

```
wget http://clark.cs.ucr.edu/Download/CLARKV1.2.6.1.tar.gz
tar -xzvf CLARKV1.2.6.1.tar.gz
cd CLARKV1.2.6.1
./install.sh
```

There were no difficulties with the installation step. After the installation took place, a module file for easier execution of the program was created.

1.1.3. Pipeline testing

The input for the Clark pipeline can be either read, contig, scaffold or transcript, as the database should commit any genomic sequence. The following is the command to create a viral database with genetic level of species:

```
set_targets.sh DB_DIR viruses --species
```

It creates a database from NCBI taxonomy for provided organisms. The database was stored inside the DB_DIR path, which is crucial for the following steps. After the database creation we run the CLARK-S classifier which was the one we were interested in. While performing the tasks from the self-written scripts placed in test/Clark directory we encountered a failure during the execution of the *classify_metagenome.sh* script, which was due to invoking the script not directly from the directory, where the script is stored. Apparently the *classify_metagenome.sh* script needs to address hidden files created inside the package directory during the database building step. These files contain the path to the database and its type (*.dbAddress*, *.DBDirectory* and *.settings files*). After adjusting the failure, by changing the directory to the Clark-S installation folder within the self-written script, the *classify_metagenome.sh* performed the classification, outputting files into *tests/Clark/classify_output* directory. Commands used during the classification step for the workflow of CLARK-S are presented below:

```
./classify_metagenome.sh -P R1_files.txt R2_files.txt -R  
Results1.txt -n 24
```

Primary classification

```
./buildSpacedDB.sh
```

Building spaced k-mers

```
./classify_metagenome.sh -P R1_file.txt R2_files.txt -R  
Results2.txt --spaced -n 24
```

Secondary classification with CLARK-S

Clark also provides the option to use multiple fasta/fastq files as the input. Paths to these files should be contained inside the one column in the input text file. If using paired end library with P flag, the sequence files should be distributed between two text files consequently R1 and R2. For the testing we choose paired end trimmed data for which we created the text files maker within the *classification_script*. The text files are in

tests/Clark/probes directory. Similarly, Clark allows the creation of the outputs text files which were also included. Last flag (*n*) stand for the number of threads used during the analysis.

Typical workflows of the program are mainly described in the *README* file inside package directory.

1.1.4. Output description

After the workflow we obtained multiple CSV files containing info about object ID, length of the object sequence, one file for each input file (for 6 fastq R1 and R2 files) producing 6 corresponding files. The next step was to estimate the abundance of the taxa provided with the viral database, which was done by the execution of the *estimate_abundance.sh* script from Clark package. Command used during the execution was oriented on the downstream analysis tool – Krona, that is an interactive web app capable of generating genetic abundance plots (repo at: <https://github.com/marbl/Krona.git>). Estimate abundance command used were:

```
./estimate_abundance -D DB_PATH -F R1_output_file R2_output_file  
--krona --highconfidence > out_file
```

Above script takes as input database path (database used during the first step of Clark pipeline – the path can be found on *.DBDirectory* file), raw output files from *classify_metagenome.sh*, multiple output files can serve as input (files were merged from primary classification with Clark and secondary classification with Clark-S). The script creates two output files. One with the statistics of classified and unclassified organisms with the name provided as standard output to the script and second – krona specific format, which was used during the downstream analysis. The krona file is always called *results.krs*, so one executing the script multiple times, once for each sample, should remember to rename the *results.krs* file after each script run. The *highconfidence* flag count only assignments with high confidence. Krona's command used to create the final output plot:

```
ImportTaxonomy -o results.html -m 3 results.krn
```

It creates standardized plot for Clark. Plots from Clark and other packages can be found in the last paragraph.

1.2. Kaiju v.1.7.3

1.2.2. Package overview

Kaiju package is written in C and C++. It is a taxonomic classifier, which uses a reference protein database from microbial and viral genomes. Kaiju translates metagenomic DNA sequences to amino acids sequences and searches for the maximal exact matches in provided database using

Burrow-Wheeler Transform. The package can use one of two modes during the execution.

- A. **Greedy mode (default)** – require higher RAM, faster and more accurate.
- B. **MEM mode** – require less RAM, faster, less accurate.

Package gives the possibility of creating multiple databases, which are fairly described in the *README* file, from which the most important are refseq and progenomes databases.

Kaiju also provides the ability to create an input for Krona (metagenomics visualization tool) - *kaiju2krona* and summarizing tool - *kaiju2table*.

1.2.3. Package installation on Okeanos

The installation step required cloning the GitHub repository of the package and compiling it with GCC compiler. Commands used during the installation:

```
git clone https://github.com/bioinformatics-centre/kaiju.git  
cd kaiju/src  
make
```

There was no problem with the installation step. After the installation took place, we created a module file for easier addressing to the program.

1.2.4. Pipeline testing

The first step during kaiju pipeline was to create a database of reference sequences. The task was accomplished with the following command:

```
kaiju-makedb -s refseq
```

Flag *s* stands for the type of the database created. This step requires approximately 100GB RAM as mentioned in manual. All database types are briefly described in GitHub main pages for the package. When invoking above command, kaiju creates the database inside the current directory. Kaiju's databases consist of three main files that need to be present before moving forward (*nodes.dmp*, *names.dmp* and *kaiju_db_*.fmi*). The next step was to classify metagenomic sequences with the main kaiju script with the command described below:

```
kaiju -t nodes.dmp -f kaiju_db_*.fmi -i R1_fastq_file -j  
R2_fastq_file -o out_file -z 24
```

First two flags are the database input files, kaiju can use both: single end and paired end sequencing input files (consequently with flag *i* and flags *i*, *j*). Last flag stands for the number of threads used during the classification.

We used default mode (greedy) to ensure the best possible classification accuracy.

1.2.5. Output description

Kaiju produces one output file per sample. The raw output must be further analyzed, the files contain multiple lines (one line for each read pair) indicating if the read pair was classified or not, containing the information about the read, assigned taxon and its mapping statistics. For further analysis kaiju output can be passed to the kaiju2krona script (installed with the package). With the following command the script produces files ready to be used as Krona input:

```
kaiju2krona -t nodes.dmp -n names.dmp -r genus -o  
kaiju_krona_out -i kaiju_output
```

Script takes as input data the database files (*t* and *n* flags), kaiju output file (flag *-i*). After that to create the Krona charts, I used:

```
ImportText -o results.html kaiju_krona_out.html
```

1.3. Kraken2 v.2.0.9

1.3.2. Package overview

Kraken2 is the second version of a program to classify DNA sequences. It creates taxonomical labels and appends them to tested sequences through the process of querying the set of k-mers from the tested genomic database. Kraken2 maps found k-mers to the lowest common ancestors of all genomes from the built database, which contains tested k-mer using a hash-table built from the database. Program contains two main scripts which are used during the analysis pipeline.

A. **kraken2** → classifier

B. **kraken2-build** → database and hash-table builder

Before classification Kraken2 requires building the hash-table from the database containing cataloged genomic sequences before the classification step. Standard databases require approximately 100GB of free disk space to build and contain the data (~70GB taxonomy of the organisms and sequences, ~30GB for the hash-table). Kraken2 supports OpenMP and multithreading.

1.3.3. Package installation on Okeanos

Kraken2 requires the usage of Linux-typical utilities like: sed, find, wget, ftp, rsync. The main script is written in PERL. For the compilation step Kraken2 requires g++ for C++11. Before the installation we switched the environment module to gnu. Installation on Okeanos moved smoothly. The

first step was to download the GitHub repo. Secondly, we run the installation script with the path to the folder for the program. And finally, created the Private module file to speed up the usage of the package. Commands used:

```
git clone https://github.com/DerrickWood/kraken2.git
cd kraken2
./install_kraken2.sh PATH
```

Where PATH variable is the path to the Program directory. To work properly Kraken2 needs additional packages to be present in the PATH variable during the execution of the main scripts. These scripts are masking low-complexity Sequences like tandem repeats. Both scripts can be found in *Blast+* package, which was also installed inside the project folder with default options covered by the tutorial in <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK279671/> from the Source tarball. The programs used by Kraken2 are *duskmasker* and *segmasker*. After successful compilation of the *Blast+* package we created the module file to add them to PATH automatically after loading the module. *Blast+* package and its module files can be found in Programy and PrivateModules directories.

1.3.3. Pipeline testing

Before the pipeline could be tested on the given data, Kraken2 needs to build a hash-table from the database. It consists of at least 3 files:

hash.k2d → the file containing minimizers for the process of mapping the taxonomy,

opts.k2d → the file containing options used during the database build process,

taxo.k2d → the file containing information about the database.

For this step we created viral database. The steps for creating the database are greatly explained in Kraken2 tutorial: <https://github.com/DerrickWood/kraken2/wiki/Manual>. Following those steps for standard database I have used following commands:

```
kraken2-build --download-taxonomy --db DB_PATH
```

```
kraken2-build --download-library viral --db DB_PATH --skip-maps
```

```
kraken2-build --build --threads 24 --db DB_PATH
```

The DB_PATH was the path to the directory, where the database was going to be stored. Custom databases like viral consists of only viral sequences, the first command download the taxonomy to the DB_PATH folder, second download viral sequences library to the same path, final flag tells program to skip the process of mapping sequences to taxonomy, which can be omitted due to downloading standardized library set like viral. Final command builds database files mentioned above. Kraken2-build supports multithreading.

Above database can be found in the *tests/KRAKEN2/db* directory (databases from other packages also are preset in their *test/package/db* directories). All custom databases were used in the classification step. Entire scripts for building the databases can be found under *tests/KRAKEN2/db_build_scripts* directory.

After the db build we performed a sanity check with the program *kraken-inspect*

```
kraken2-inspect --db DB_PATH
```

For the classification step we tried running the kraken for a one probe inside the interactive bash shell. After the confirmation that the package works, we wrote a script for the pipeline for multiple probes with the same suffix. The scripts for Kraken can be found in *tests/KRAKEN2/Classification_scripts* also they are uploaded to the git repository for the apprenticeship. The scripts can be reused after the variable adjustments. Here are the commands for the Kraken2 classification:

```
kraken2 --report REPORT --threads 24 --db DB_PATH --memory-mapping --paired R1_fastq R2_fastq --otuput OUTPUT_PATH --no-masking
```

Flag *--report* creates a report in different format than the regular one. Flag *--threads* supports multithreading with OpenMP, flag *--memory-mapping* permits Kraken2 to load the hash-table to RAM, flag *--paired* for paired-end files, finally with *--output* we specify output file. Kraken2 uses an auto-detection tool to check the format of the given sequences. Kraken2 does not expect any preliminary input adjustments like trimming, nor extracting non-human sequences. Unfortunately, Kraken2 had to be run without the Blast+ scripts with *-no-masking* flag. (otherwise, program outputted only unclassified sequences)

We classified the sequences from all files and probes in the provided data. Outputs of the classification are in the */tests/KRAKEN2/Classify/* folders. These files could be examined further by one of Related Tools for Downstream Analysis like *Bracken*, *KrakenTools*, *Pavian* or *Krona*.

1.3.4. Output description

For downstream analysis we used *KrakenTools* and *Krona* packages. *Kraken2* regular output resembles *kaiju* output (almost the same information mentioned in both files). *Kraken2* report shows cladograms of identified sequences. Report can be analyzed further by *KrakenTools* (repo at <https://github.com/jenniferlu717/KrakenTools.git>) *kreport2krona* script which produces output file ready to be used to visualize the genetic abundance with *Krona*. It was achieved with the following commands:

```
kreport2krona.py -r REPORT -o kraken2_krona.out  
ImportText kraken2_krona.out -o kraken2_krona.out.html
```

1.4. *Metaphlan2 v.2.7.7*

1.4.2. *Package overview*

Metaphlan2 is another tool for profiling metagenomic environments. The package checks for unique clade-specific marker genes identified in approximately 17.000 reference genomes. The tool is written in python.

1.4.3. *Package installation on Okeanos*

Package requires following tools:

- A. Python version 2.7 or higher, although via miniconda it could not be installed when the environment python version was 3.X or higher, thus I presume that it works only with python 2.
- B. Additional python packages:
 - a. Argparse, tempfile (presumably installed with the environment)
 - b. Numpy, Bowtie2 (needs to be installed before installing Metaphlan2)
 - c. Pandas, BioPython, Scipy, Mathplotlib, biom, hclust2 (optional packages)

Metaphlan2 can be installed via the package manager like Anaconda. Unfortunately running Anaconda environment from the scripts can be more difficult to achieve. The first step during the installation was to install Miniconda 4.8.3 package manager via following commands:

```
wget https://repo.anaconda.com/miniconda/Miniconda3-latest-Linux-x86\_64.sh  
bash Miniconda3-latest-Linux-x86_64.sh -b -p PATH -f
```

where flags correspond to: silent mode (*b*) localization (*p*) - where the package should be installed, (*f*) forcing the installation in the directory already created.

After that, we initialized the package and created the environment `Metagenomics_env`.

```
./conda init bash  
Source ~/.bashrc  
Conda create -name Metagenomics_env python=2.7  
Conda activate Metagenomics_env  
Conda install -c bioconda/label/cf201901 metaphlan2
```

These commands install miniconda with python 2.7 and metaphlan2 with its dependencies.

1.4.4. Pipeline testing

Metaphlan2 does not require any database before execution but running it through the script with package manager environment is more difficult. It needs additional lines of code before invoking the classification script:

```
eval "$(conda shell.bash hook)"  
conda activate Metagenomics_env
```

After these commands in the shell script, we can invoke Metaphlan2 directly from it.

```
Metaphlan2.py R1_fastq,R2_fastq -bowtie2out BOWTIE_OUT --nprocs  
24 --input_type fastq > Metaphlan2_classification_output
```

The program can use both single end and paired end datasets, paired end files should be separated by a comma. Program outputs to standard output, one shall always say what input files are being expected, the list of manageable input formats is described in user manual. Program supports multithreading. Additional output from Bowtie2 helps if the analysis needs to re rerun (did not use that output, but it is required as program without specifying this flag stops executing).

1.4.5. Output description

Metaphlan2 standard output is a tsv file of the predicted taxon relative abundances. It can be analyzed further by various tools like *StainPhlan*, *GraPhlan*, *Hclust2*, *Krona*. We choose the last one as it *was also chosen for other programs*. To create an abundance cladogram, we used *metaphlan2krona.py* script to create Krona input files and then created abundance plot.

```
metaphlan2krona.py -p Metaphlan2_classification_output -k  
Metaphlan2_krona.out  
ImportText Metaphlan2_krona.out -o Metaphalan2_krona.out.html.
```

1.5. SPAdes v.3.14.1

1.5.2. Package overview

SPAdes package is a genomic assembler tool providing multiple workflow pipelines:

- A. **MetaSPAdes** → metagenomic assembler used in this analysis.
- B. **PlasimdSPAdes** → tool for plasmid identification WGS data sets.

- C. **MetaplasmidSPAdes** → like PlasmidSPAdes but using metagenomic data sets.
- D. **RNASPAdes** → *de novo* RNA-Seq data assembler.
- E. **TrueSPAdes** → TrueSeq barcode assembler.
- F. **BiosyntheticSPAdes** → Biosynthetic gene cluster assembler.

For the pipeline testing, we used only the first assembly tool – MetaSPAdes. SPAdes package is written mainly in C++ and C languages. Additional assembly tools are written in Python. It supports Python version 2.7 and Python3 version 3.2 and higher. SPAdes input can be paired-and reads, made-pairs and unpaired reads. The read’s length can vary, and SPAdes can use Illumina, IonTorrent, PacBio, Oxford Nanopore and Sanger reads.

1.5.3. Package installation on Okeanos

SPAdes can be installed in two ways. It can be compiled or downloaded with binaries. In both situations, SPAdes require one of the Python versions described above. On the other hand, compilation also requires g++ version 5.3.1 or higher, cmake version 3.5 or higher, zlib and libbz2 packages. The standard packages installed on Okeanos are missing the libbz2, which needed to be installed firstly. We downloaded the source code for the SPAdes package and tried to compile it with all available GNU compilers. Unfortunately, compilation process has been giving errors while trying to link header files. For that reason, we downloaded binary files which also didn’t need libbz2 package to be loaded into the path variables. We installed the packages with following commands:

```
wget http://cab.spbu.ru/files/release3.14.1/SPAdes-3.14.1-Linux.tar.gz
tar -xzf SPAdes-3.14.1-Linux.tar.gz
```

Finally, we created the module file for the package.

1.5.4. Pipeline testing

SPAdes is not a metagenomic sequence classifier, thus it cannot be compared to the other packages presented in this report. Its main goal is to *de novo* assemble genomic sequences from raw reads. Similarly, MetaSPAdes assembles metagenomic sequences but does not make any taxonomic classification. MetaSPAdes pipeline consists of invoking SPAdes.py with flag --meta. It supports multithreading (---threads). For testing the pipeline, we used paired-and data sets. The PE file paths are given after the flags -1 and -2 respectively. SPAdes also consider the amount of RAM allocated to its execution. We used the following command:

```
spades.py --meta -1 R1_fastq -2 R2_fastq -o out --threads24 --memory 120
```

We also used unpaired data set by specifying the flag `-s` to the input file within a previous command.

1.5.5. Output description

In both situations (with paired end files and unmapped files) SPAdes gave errors. In the first situation SPAdes required larger amount of RAM than maximum of 120 GB allowed on Okeanos and it did not manage to finish the analysis and produce assembly files. Addressing the second issue, SPAdes could not use a single input file for the analysis. It needed to be present at least both paired end files in addition to unmapped input file.

1.6. QUAST v.5.0.2

1.6.2. Package overview

QUAST package is also created for genomic assemblies. MetaQUAST is a part of QUAST package. It is used for evaluating metagenomic assemblies. It is not a classification tool. For input, QUAST needs assembled contigs, that might be produced by assemble tool like MetaSPAdes. QUAST is written in C++, Perl, Python and C. QUAST outputs multiple metrics plots and reports. It can also produce graphical output in form of Icarus (written in HTML and Javascript).

1.6.3. Package installation on Okeanos

Packages requirements are Python2 version 2.5 or Python3 version 3.5 or higher, GSS compiler version 4.7 or higher, Perl version 5.6.0 or higher, GNUmake and AR, zlib library. Basic installation requires downloading source code and extracting it. QUAST precompiles all its components on its first use. For that reason, installation is not required, but can be managed through execution of the installation scripts. We installed QUAST with the following commands:

```
Git clone https://github.com/ablab/quast.git  
cd quast  
./setup.py install_full
```

After that, we created module file for the package.

1.6.4. Pipeline testing

Before the tests, we created the list of reference sequences genome names, each one on the separate line with the simple self-written Python script. (names retrieved from NCBI refseq viral database). Text file containing all the names was used as a reference list within a metaQUAST pipeline. QUAST input is like the one used in a SPAdes package. It uses

paired-and data set with the flags -1, -2, R1_fastq and R2_fastq, respectively. Unfortunately, QUASt also needs a genomic assembly file to evaluate, presumably created with SPAdes or another genomic assembler (Velvet, SOAPdenovo, VgA). We tried to make an analysis without them, but it was unsuccessful giving an error about the missing assembly files.

2. Repository

Following the tests, we created a GitLab repository for facilitating the installation process on Okeanos. Heap_pipelines repository contains following packages: kraken2 version 2.0.9, kaiju version 1.7.3, Clark version 1.2.6.1, Metaphlan2 version 2.7.7, QUASt version 5.0.2, SPAdes version 3.14.1 and their dependencies when needed – blast+ and miniconda. The repository was created in GitLab-icm. Heap_pipelines repository contains following project directories:

- A. **ModuleFiles** → Directory, where are stored tcl module files for the packages to be installed.
- B. **.InstallScripts** → Directory, where are stored scripts responsible for each process of package installation.
- C. **Additional_scripts** → Directory where are stored self-written scripts used during the tests on Okeanos.
 - a. **Classify_script** → Scripts used for the classification step.
 - b. **Db_scripts** → Scripts used for the database creation step.
 - c. **GetReference.py** → Script used for the creation of reference list file for QUASt.
- D. **.MakeProjectDirectories.sh** → Script responsible for creating directories for packages and TemporaryFiles
- E. **MainInstallationScript.sh** → Script responsible for the installation of the packages.

and additional directories created by *.MakeProjectDirectories.sh* script:

- F. **Programs** → Directory, where the packages are installed.
- G. **TemporaryFiles** → Directory with temporary files downloaded during the installation of the packages.

To install the packages, clone the repository from:

```
git clone https://git.icm.edu.pl/ss426665/heap\_pipelines.git
cd heap_pipelines
./MainInstallationScript.sh
```

The package needs further tests and improvements for catching exceptions and management of the package versions.

Test scripts introduced inside *Additional_scripts* directory, are exemplary and should be adjusted via paths and variables before execution.

4 Pipeline results

In the next couple of pages, I present results from all tested pipelines in a form of Krona abundance charts:

Figure 2
Kaiju

Figure 4 Metaphlan2

Rest of the cladograms can be found in supplementary data. Full interactive web Krona charts are positioned in Praktyki directory under path DataForKronaTools/KronaOutputs.

3. 6. Results and further outcomes

6.1. Results

The installation of all the mentioned metagenomic packages was successful. Following that all the packages were tested on Okeanos with 24 threads (when possible multithreading), 120 GB of RAM on a single node, using paired end, trimmed and quality filtered samples from TCGA cervical cancer dataset. Four packages (CLARK, Kraken2, kaiju and Metaphlan2) were tested successfully. SPAdes analysis was unsuccessful due to a lack of RAM (maximal 120 GB default on Okeanos nodes was not enough to *de novo* assemble the metagenomics contigs). QUASt follows the previous failure because it cannot be executed without the contigs assembly files.

The most difficult and complex analysis was one with the Clark, because of the challenges presented during the scripts debugging process. (information about running Clark domestic scripts – `classify_metagenome.sh` `build_spacedDB.sh` needs to be executed directly from the Clark's installation directory is missing from the website and README file and script manuals). Another handicap was encountered during the installation of metaphlan2 via the miniconda package manager (difficulty in invoking metaphlan2 commands from the environment inside the sbatch scripts causing dump cores in couple occasions – issue not addressed further, as I was able to conduct the analysis).

The fastest analysis was conducted by Metaphlan2 although it was the least accurate. As it can be seen on the cladograms Metaphlan2 discovered the least amount of viral sequences, all other programs were much better. It also classified bacterial taxa in the presented probe. In other two Metaphlan2 found only viral sequences, but could not divide them into clads, only found LCA. Kaiju presented better results, but not as accurate as Clark and Kraken2. The most accurate and the slowest was Kraken2. It discovered the largest amount of viral sequences in provided dataset.

6.2. Further outcomes

Following the testing step, we created a repository facilitating the installation process of the packages mentioned above on Okeanos. Hopefully, it will allow to continue work with the metagenomics classification tools in the future. Repository can be found in: https://git.icm.edu.pl/ss426665/heap_pipelines

6 Literature

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